

As on 20-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended for recording uses and derived product data into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to understand the context of the crops uses in several sources and find examples of the products derived from the crops.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - **'Uses'** is the main table for recording the uses of a specific crop and **'Derived Products'** is the child table for recording the products that derived or developed based on the uses entered.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. **IMPORTANT:** Prior to data entry, one has to ensure that the crop data that is going to be entered does not exist in record of the database.
3. In the **'Uses'** table, there are 5 fields to be entered, **four** of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

3.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the common name which belongs to a specific crop subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace.

3.2 Part (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the part of crop that is used for a specific uses.
- Select 'Whole' if all parts of crop are used for specific uses.
- It is possible for one part to have multiple uses and one uses has multiple parts.

3.3 Use Category (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the category of crop uses.

3.4 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the uses of a specific crop itself.

3.5 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to the metadata of alternative names.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

4. In the '**Crop Derived Product**' table, there are 5 fields to be entered, **three** of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

- 4.1 Uses ID (Auto-generated)

- This is referring to the unique ID of the record in the 'Crop Records' table.

- 4.2 Product name (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the name of product which was derived from the previously entered uses.

- 4.3 Product Description

- This is referring to the explanation about the derived product.

- 4.4 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the derived product of a specific crop itself.

- 4.5 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to the metadata of alternative names.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.